

Holographic informational membrane and M-theory

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Abstract

In this paper, we consider the interpretation of M-theory based on the holographic principle. A simple analysis gives the following result. Particle energy is proportional to the density of holographic information in space. This definition suggests that fundamental particles are informational two-dimensional membranes.

Previously, David Bohm developed the idea of a holographic reality of the space of the Universe. This idea was reflected in the holographic principle in the works of T Hooft, Susskind, Bekenstein, Hawking. Hawking's main discovery was to predict the temperature of a black hole

$$T_H = \frac{c^3 h}{8\pi k G M}$$

This means a black hole emits particles with energy

$$E = k T_H = \frac{c^3 h}{8\pi G M} = \frac{c h}{4\pi r_g}$$

On the other hand, the surface of a black hole is proportional to the holographic information

$$I_{max} = \frac{c^3 A}{4Gh}$$

This is the holographic principle.

When a black hole emits a particle, its surface and volume decreases, and information also decreases

$$\Delta V = 4\pi r^2 \Delta r = \frac{r}{2} \Delta A$$

$$\Delta I_{max} = \frac{c^3 \Delta A}{4Gh} = \frac{c^3 \Delta V}{2Gh r}$$

The result is a connection between the particle energy, holographic information and the size of the space.

$$E = \frac{c h}{4\pi r_g} = \frac{G h^2}{2\pi c^2} \frac{\Delta I_{max}}{\Delta V}$$

We conclude that particles are geometric information objects. Moreover, it is necessary to clarify the nature of this geometry.

Consider the particle energy as a carrier of information density

$$E \approx \frac{Gh^2}{c^2} \frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} \rightarrow \frac{Gh^2}{c^2} \frac{\partial f_{ik}}{\partial x^j}$$

Where can be split into metric definition of information

$$I = -\ln P$$

In the form of the Fisher information metric

$$f_{ik} = \frac{\partial^2 I}{\partial x_i \partial x_k} = -\frac{\partial^2 \ln P}{\partial x_i \partial x_k}$$

This gives a geometric definition of information. Now we can introduce the concept of connectedness for the Fisher metric. This is the basic concept of differential information geometry.

$$\Gamma_{ikj} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial f_{ik}}{\partial x^j} + \frac{\partial f_{ij}}{\partial x^k} - \frac{\partial f_{kj}}{\partial x^i} \right)$$

We introduce the surface in the coordinate direction

$$dA_x = dx dz$$

Then the average distribution of information is defined as an integral over an open or closed surface

$$\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta V} \approx \int f^{kj} \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial f_{ik}}{\partial x^j} + \frac{\partial f_{ij}}{\partial x^k} - \frac{\partial f_{kj}}{\partial x^i} \right) dA_i$$

As a result, the particle energy will be a topological integral over the surface of information geometry of any kind

$$E = \frac{Gh^2}{c^2} \int f^{kj} \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial f_{ik}}{\partial x^j} + \frac{\partial f_{ij}}{\partial x^k} - \frac{\partial f_{kj}}{\partial x^i} \right) dA_i = \frac{Gh^2}{c^2} \int f^{kj} \Gamma_{ikj} dA_i$$

This definition suggests that fundamental particles are informational two-dimensional membranes. The action of this object is

$$S = - \int E dt = - \frac{Gh^2}{c^2} \int f^{kj} \Gamma_{ikj} dA_i dt$$

Where the tension of the information membrane is obtained in the form

$$T_i = \frac{dE}{dA_i} = \frac{Gh^2}{c^2} f^{kj} \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial f_{ik}}{\partial x^j} + \frac{\partial f_{ij}}{\partial x^k} - \frac{\partial f_{kj}}{\partial x^i} \right)$$

We do not forget that the fundamental information itself is the basis of a two-dimensional membrane.

$$-\Delta \ln P = \Delta I$$

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